

Data Logging System for the Electro-Hydraulic Governor Control System at Hunterston B Power Station

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ABSTRACT

In a nuclear generating power station, data acquisition and storage is necessary for various sections of the station, as part of the data scanning and alarm monitoring for the entire station. It also allows tracing and evaluation of problems that cause a disruption in the power generation process at the station.

The data logging system for the Electro-Hydraulic Governor (EHG) equipment at British Energy's Hunterston 'B' Power Station in West Kilbride, Scotland, where this Masters dissertation was carried out, is obsolete and unsustainable and this has necessitated the development of a data logging system for the EHG using LabVIEW software, to replace the current data logging system. It is also necessary to enhance the functionality of the current data logging system to include real time logging of important plant parameters as their values change with time.

Speed signals to test the Electro-Hydraulic Governor for overspeed during a maintenance outage at the station need to be simulated using LabVIEW to eliminate the use of *function generators* to carry out such a test.

Secure ways of accessing this useful data from remote authorised locations of the station need to be suggested as well.

DEDICATION

This dissertation is dedicated to my family for their constant love, support and understanding.

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GLOSSARY OF ACRONYMS:

ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
AGR	Advanced Gas-Cooled Reactor
AVR	Automatic Voltage Regulator
CSMA/CD	Carrier Sense Multiple Access/Collision Detection
CCR	Central Control Room
CMR	Continuous Maximum Rating
DAQ	Data Acquisition
DCE	Data Communications Equipment
DCS	Distributed Control System
DSP	Digital Signal Processing
DTE	Data Terminal Equipment
EHG	Electro Hydraulic Governor
ESV	Emergency Stop Valve
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
HP	High Pressure
IP	Intermediate Pressure
JTF	Joint Time-Frequency
LabVIEW	Laboratory Virtual Instrumentation Engineering Workbench
LP	Low Pressure
MBFPT	Main Boiler Feedpump Turbine
MSC	Median Select Controller

MT	Main Turbine
NI	National Instruments
OLVT	On-Load Valve Testing
RESV	Reheat Emergency Stop Valve
SSBFP	Start and Standby Boiler Feedpump
USB	Universal Serial Bus
VHDL	Very (<i>High Speed Integrated Circuits</i>) H ardware D escription L anguage
VI	Virtual Instrument

DEFINITION OF TERMS:

Advanced Gas-Cooled Reactors: In these reactors, steam produced from a regulated chain reaction is used to power turbines to generate electricity (British Energy, 2009).

Chain Reaction: Chain reactions occur when the neutrons emitted from a nuclear fission come into contact with more uranium atoms, thereby sparking off another nuclear fission reaction and the process continues (British Energy, 2009).

Data Logging: Data logging, in instrumentation and control processes, is the process of collecting different information such as physical parameters like temperature, pressure, rate of flow, voltage to monitor or control the process.

Function Generators: A function generator is an electronic device or software used in generating electrical waveforms.

Nuclear Fission Reaction: A reaction involving the splitting of Uranium atoms into two nearly equal parts with the emission of heat and extra neutrons (British Energy, 2009).

Resolver: The resolver is an AC device that requires a Driver Unit to energise its primary winding and condition the resulting secondary winding signal to produce an output signal proportional to the actuator position (Hunterston 'B' Power Station Training Manual).

Superheated steam: Steam is superheated when it is at a temperature which is higher than the boiling point of water.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Electricity production in coal, oil and nuclear power stations are similar. These power stations produce steam that is used to drive a turbine to generate electricity. It is important that vital data like speed, generated load, and other useful parameters that provide useful information about the health of different units of a power generation stations, are constantly logged and monitored to ensure continued optimum performance of the units. In the event of a trip in a nuclear power station resulting in a disruption in power generation, reference can be made to the history of logged data prior to the trip occurring, to investigate likely causes of the trip with the aim of correcting the faults detected.

The current method of data logging at Hunterston ‘B’ Nuclear Power Station is obsolete and unsustainable because and the printer used to print the logged data is defective. There is therefore a need to implement a modern replacement system to acquire and log vital plant parameters.

Different engineers on site require the logged parameters to carry out their day to day job and access to the logged data from different locations on plant is necessary. This logged data is sensitive and the serious security requirements of a nuclear station make it necessary to implement a secure strategy that would allow only authorised engineers at the company to access the logged data.

1.1 BRIEF OVERVIEW OF THE POWER GENERATION PROCESS AT HUNTERSTON ‘B’:

Hunterston ‘B’ Power Station with a generating capacity of 660 Megawatts (MW) is one of UK’s first *Advanced Gas-Cooled Reactor (AGR)* nuclear power stations. Here, a controlled *chain reaction* produces enough heat energy that converts water into steam. The steam produced powers turbines which then drives the electrical generators (Scobie et al, 1979; British Energy, 2009).

Hunterston ‘B’ Power Station is situated on the Firth of Clyde, ensuring availability of seawater for use in the plant. The seawater is used to condense steam from the turbines into water. Any surplus heat energy which is not used in producing electricity is absorbed by the seawater. Before the seawater reaches the station system, it is

filtered using water filters of varying sizes to ensure that no aquatic life enters the station system. Cooling water pumps send the filtered seawater through the condenser (Scobie et al, 1979; British Energy, 2009).

Unused steam from the turbine is condensed back into water (feedwater) and sent back to the boilers where it is reused. The feedwater is pumped back to the boilers at flow rates reaching 500 litres per second by Feedwater pumps. Within the reactor, gas pumps circulate carbon dioxide which transfers heat energy from the fuel to the boilers, where water is boiled and subsequently superheated (British Energy, 2009).

Over 1.5 Giga watts (1.5 billion watts) of heat energy is produced by the *nuclear fission* reaction that occurs in reactor core which is housed in the 4 metre-thick concrete pressure vessel. The pressure vessel provides shielding from radiation (British Energy, 2009).

A network of thousands of steel pipes provides a heat exchange system, boiling 500 litres of water per second. Steam from the boiler gets to the HP turbine at a pressure of over 150 times atmospheric pressure and temperature of over 540 degrees Celsius (British Energy, 2009).

Superheated steam from the boiler is routed, through pipes, to the high pressure (HP) turbines and nozzles direct the steam onto the blades, attached to a shaft, which causes the turbines to rotate. The steam is sent back to the boilers to be re-heated before being sent onto the intermediate-pressure (IP) turbine and from the IP it is sent to the low-pressure (LP) turbines, which is the final point of energy generation for the steam (British Energy, 2009).

The standard frequency of electricity in the UK is 50 Hertz (50 cycles per second or 3000 cycles per minute). A generator consisting of a large hydrogen cooled electro-magnet (rotor) is driven by the turbine at a speed of 3000 revolutions per minute (rpm) inside a water-cooled electrical winding (stator). The revolving magnetic field of the rotor generates electricity in the stator windings at 23 kilo Volts (British Energy, 2009; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual). *Appendix A* depicts the power generation process in an AGR nuclear power station.

The generator is associated with two modes of operation, namely the un-synchronised and the synchronised modes. In the un-synchronised mode, the generator is

disconnected from the National Grid System and energy supplied to the turbine at this point controls the turbine speed (British Energy, 2009; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

When the generator is connected to the National Grid, it is operating in the synchronised mode and the grid frequency sets the speed of the turbine. At this point, extra energy fed to the turbine appears as load. The Electro-Hydraulic Governor (EHG) controls the speed of the turbine in the un-synchronised mode and the turbine load in the synchronised mode (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

The generator runs at a speed of 3000 rpm when it is synchronised to the grid and at this point a change in power output would not result in a change in alternator speed.

1.2 DATA LOGGING SYSTEM AT HUNTERSTON 'B' POWER STATION:

The EHG Control System, which controls the flow of steam to the turbine, is located in an air conditioned room beside the high pressure end of the turbine. The set of channels, the set title, individual channel titles and engineering units, together with the date and time are all displayed on the computer monitor screen on the EHG Control System.

The already formatted blocks of data that appear on the computer monitor screen, as shown in *Figure 1.1*, is sent to the *LA75 Plus Companion* Printer in form of *ASCII* streams, by issuing appropriate instructions to the EHG system. The 'page select' button on the EHG selects the page to print and 'page print' button sends the data to the printer for printing. Logged data is therefore presented as *demand* print (Scobie et al, 1979).

The printer is connected to the EHG via a 100 Ohm 4 pair File Transfer Protocol (FTP) Serial Cable, terminated with a serial cable jack on the printer end and terminated with a 25-way D type connector at the EHG end.

This method of data logging is obsolete and unsustainable because the final print document consists of a substantial number of blank pages. The printer is also not efficient as it is slow and there is frequent occurrence of paper 'jams'.

It has become necessary to log the data that would otherwise have been sent to the printer onto a file on a computer system. This is to allow a user to format the data before sending it to a printer.

Figure 1.1: EHG Monitor showing a screen of displayed parameters.

1.3 DESCRIPTION OF PLANT ITEMS:

Brief descriptions of important plant items that provide the EHG Control System with various parameters are given below:

1.3.1 MAIN TURBINE GENERATOR:

Hunterston 'B' Main Turbine EHG, which is manufactured by Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, is designed to control the main turbine generator by means of four HP governor valves and four intercept valves to provide specific control modes and facilities. The main turbine is a horizontal five stage machine that comprises of a single flow high pressure (HP) turbine, a double flow intermediate pressure (IP) turbine and three double flow low pressure (LP) turbines. The turbine shafts are coupled together rigidly in line and positioned axially by a thrust assembly between the HP and IP turbines. Steam sealed turbine shaft glands are provided to prevent leakage of steam, at the points where the shafts emerge from the casings. (Rolls Royce Operating and Maintenance Manual, 1998; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual)

1.3.2 HIGH PRESSURE (HP) TURBINE:

The HP turbine receives steam from the boiler through the HP steam chests. Steam inlets are situated at the end of the HP cylinder and beside the IP turbine. The steam flow into the HP turbine is in a direction away from the generator (*Figure 1.3*).

Steam that passes through the HP turbine is passed on to the reheater via exhaust connections (Rolls Royce Operating and Maintenance Manual, 1998; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

1.3.3 INTERMEDIATE PRESSURE (IP) TURBINE:

The steam coming from the reheater is passed through the reheat steam chests to the IP turbine in a similar fashion to the HP turbine. Steam from the IP turbine is exhausted through large diameter pipes to three LP turbines as shown in *Figure 1.3* (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

1.3.4 LOW PRESSURE (LP) TURBINE:

The steam which is exhausted from the IP turbine is passed to the inlets of the three double flow LP turbines. Steam from the LP turbine is exhausted into the pannier condenser and a part of steam flow through each LP turbine is tapped off for regenerative feed heating (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

Figure 1.2: Internal structure of HP, IP and LP Turbine (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual)

Figure 1.3: HP, IP and LP turbines showing direction of steam flow (Hunterston ‘B’ Training Manual)

1.3.5 HIGH PRESSURE STEAM CHEST:

Steam to the HP turbine is provided by two HP steam chests, one on each side of the HP turbine. Each steam chest consists of two emergency/stop valves (ESVs) and two governor valves which control steam supply to the HP turbine through interconnecting pipes.

1.3.6 HIGH PRESSURE EMERGENCY STOP VALVE (ESVs):

The ESVs cut off the steam supply to the HP turbine during unusual conditions. The ESVs are either fully open under normal turbine operating conditions or are fully closed, to stop flow of steam, when there is turbine trip. The ESVs are four in number (Hunterston ‘B’ Training Manual).

1.3.7 MAIN TURBINE GOVERNOR VALVES:

Four governor valves control the flow of steam to the HP turbine through interconnecting pipes. The governor valves are only about 2% open when admitting steam to increase the speed of the main turbine from barring speed (30 rpm) to

synchronisation speed (3000 rpm). After synchronisation, the governor valves determine the loading of the machine. The governor valves are fully shut in the event of a trip. The main turbine governor valves are shown in *Figure 1.4* below.

Figure 1.4: Main Turbine Governor Valves (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual)

1.3.8 REHEAT STEAM CHESTS:

Two reheat steam chests are provided, one on each side of the IP turbine. Each reheat steam chest contains two reheat emergency/stop valves and two intercept valves.

Two tubular support assemblies hold the steam chests in place and this arrangement enables the chest to move in a horizontal plane, allowing axial and transverse expansion.

1.3.9 REHEAT EMERGENCY STOP VALVES (RESVS):

The RESVs immediately stop admission of steam to the IP turbine in an emergency. They are fully open under normal turbine operating conditions and are fully closed in the event of a turbine trip. There are four RESVs in number (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

1.3.10 INTERCEPT VALVES:

Four intercept valves control the flow of steam to the IP turbine through interconnecting pipes. The intercept valves are control valves in the same sense as the

governor valves but are about 20% open initially. The intercept valves are also fully closed in the event of a turbine trip (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

1.3.11 MAIN BOILER FEEDPUMP TURBINE (MBFPT):

Hunterston 'B' Boiler Feedpump EHG system, which is housed in the same cubicle as the main turbine EHG, is designed to control the MBFPT speed by means of two MBFPT governor valves to provide specific control modes and facilities. The MBFPT has a 16-stage horizontal blade system and uses bled off steam from the HP turbine exhaust. (South of Scotland Electricity Board, 2003; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual)

1.3.12 MAIN BOILER FEEDPUMP GOVERNOR VALVES:

The main boiler feedpump governor valves control the admission of steam to the main boiler feedpump turbine and are fully shut when there is a main boiler feedpump turbine trip (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual). *Figure 1.5* below shows the main boiler feedpump governor valves.

Figure 1.5: Main Boiler Feedpump Governor Valves (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual)

1.3.13 MAIN BOILER FEEDPUMP EMERGENCY STOP VALVES:

The main boiler feedpump ESVs operate in a similar manner to the main turbine ESVs. They are fully open during normal running of the feedpump turbine to allow steam to the system and are fully shut when there is a feedpump turbine trip (South of Scotland Electricity Board, 2003; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

1.3.14 BARRING GEAR:

The barring gear rotates the turbine shafts before turbine run-up and also after shut-down of the turbine to prevent uneven cooling or heating of the turbine shafts which results in bending of the shaft. This can lead to damage of the fixed and moving turbine parts. The barring gear is driven by an electric motor and in the event of a failure, is driven manually or by air. The barring speed for the main turbine (*Figure 1.6*) is 30 rpm (revolutions per minute) while that of the boiler feedpump turbine (*Figure 1.7*) is 100 rpm (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

Figure 1.6: Main Turbine Barring Gear (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual)

Figure 1.7: Main Boiler Feedpump Turbine and Barring Gear (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual)

1.4 ELECTRO-HYDRAULIC GOVERNOR (EHG):

The Electro-Hydraulic Governor (EHG) Control System, shown in *Figure 1.9*, is a closed loop, real time multi-processor digital control system that controls turbine speed whilst the generator is un-synchronised and load, once the machine is synchronised. It achieves this by controlling the position of the governor and intercept valves. In the un-synchronised state, the generator is disconnected from the National Grid System and any energy delivered to the turbine in the form of steam influences the speed of the machine. After synchronisation and connection to the National Grid, the turbine speed is determined by the grid frequency and any extra energy supplied to the turbine will appear as load (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

The EHG computes control algorithms from different parameters (for example, start-up parameters like speed setpoint) used to monitor and control the turbine. These parameters are mainly static parameters and are available on demand. The parameters are displayed on the EHG monitor screen and can be sent to the printer in the EHG Control Room for printing (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

Four HP governor valves and IP intercept valves, each with its own Median Select Controller (MSC), provide modulating control. Each MSC receives a demand signal from each of the 3 channels and provides individual closed loop control on the median value of the three signals (British Energy Generation Ltd., 2003; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

Figure 1.8: EHG Control Action

There is a comparison between the selected demand signal and actuator position feedback signal from which a servo drive signal is derived which controls the actuator in a manner that cancels out the error between demand and actuator position. An electronic position *resolver* system provides the position feedback from the valve thereby closing the loop to the MSC. Each of the independent MSC control loops is thus supervised and controlled by the three governor control channels. *Figure 1.8* shows a block diagram of the EHG control action.

The three channels operate in a redundancy configuration such that any two out of three (2oo3) channels will maintain full control but failure of two channels will result in a turbine trip.

The EHG is operated in speed mode during run up or shut down. It controls turbine speed from barring speed (about 30 rpm for the main turbine) to synchronous speed (3000 rpm). After synchronisation, the speed set point controls are automatically converted to operate as load set point controls and the EHG loads the machine with 20 Megawatts block load (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

The EHG can then operate to a demand signal derived from the Distributed Control System (DCS) and communicated to the EHG via the serial link.

Figure 1.9: Electro-Hydraulic Governor Control System with monitor for visual display.

1.41 FUNCTIONS OF THE EHG:

The EHG also offers the following protection features:

- (i) If the condenser vacuum drops, the EHG can automatically runback load or speed (unload) and bring the machine to a safe operating level. Vacuum is maintained for efficiency and to protect the LP cylinders and blades (Hunterston 'B' Plant Maintenance Manual, 2001).
- (ii) **Load runback when there is a quadrant trip:** Four reactor quadrants exist. A quadrant trip arises when temperature from the boilers in three of the four quadrants falls outside specified range.
- (iii) Load runback when there is a trip in the feed heating system (Hunterston 'B' Plant Maintenance Manual, 2001; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

(iv) **Acceleration detection above 9% per second:** The turbine may accelerate above that rate when there is loss of electrical load for instance. When this happens, the governor valves and intercept valves are closed until the acceleration is checked. If the acceleration persists above 9% per second, an overspeed condition results and the turbine is tripped to prevent mechanical damage (Hunterston 'B' Plant Maintenance Manual, 2001; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

(v) **On Load Valve Testing (OLVT):** Stroke testing of the steam valves is carried out, one at a time, when the set is on-load. This is achieved by overriding the signal to each valve, individually (Hunterston 'B' Plant Maintenance Manual, 2001). OLVT is used to check the following valves:

- Main Turbine Emergency Stop Valves (ESVs)
- Main Turbine Reheat Emergency Stop Valves (RESVs)
- Main Turbine Governor Valves
- Main Turbine Intercept Valves
- Boiler Feed Pump Turbine Emergency Stop Valves
- Boiler Feed Pump Turbine Governor Valves

(vi) **Interlock to start Barring Gear and Jacking Oil pumps:** The jacking oil supplies oil at high pressure below particular journals of the generator, preventing metal-to-metal contact between a journal and its bearing. This significantly reduces static friction and bearing wear. The torque required to start the motor is also reduced. The interlocks prevent turning unless the hydrogen seal pressures are normal and the bearing oil pressure is satisfactory (Hunterston 'B' Plant Maintenance Manual, 2001; British Energy Generation Ltd, 2003).

1.4.2 DESCRIPTION AND CHARACTERISATION OF EHG PARAMETERS FROM THE MAIN TURBINE:

1.4.2.1 SPEED AND SPEED SETPOINT FOR RUN UPS:

During a sequence run-up, the run up rate selected from the six controlled speed run-up programmes shown in *Table 1.1* depends mainly on the temperature of the HP cylinder. The speed set-point is controlled using the setpoint control speed/load raise/lower button. After synchronisation, the speed setpoint is fixed at 3000 rpm.

The rated speed of the main turbine is 3000 rpm and it has a barring speed of 30 rpm. The speed is represented by analogue signals but the speed setpoint is represented by an incremental digital signal.

Table 1.1: Turbine run-up speed rates adjustable parameters (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998)

RATE NO.	RATE (RPM/MIN)
1	43
2	50
3	300
4	600
5	600
6	600

1.4.2.2 LOAD AND LOAD SETPOINT:

The turbine loading rates (*Table 1.2*) also depend on the temperature of the turbine and this is to reduce stress and prevent uneven expansion. After synchronisation, the raise/lower buttons which control the speed setpoint are now used to control the load setpoint. The *Continuous Maximum Rating (CMR)* of the turbine is 660 MW but the load setpoint is usually set at about 75% of CMR at Hunterston 'B' Power Station. An analogue signal is used to represent the load and the load setpoint is represented by an incremental digital signal.

Table 1.2: Turbine loading rate adjustable parameters (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998)

RATE NO.	RATE (% CMR/MIN) LOW LOAD	RATE (% CMR/MIN) HIGH LOAD
1	0.6	0.9
2	0.5	1.1
3	0.6	1.4
4	2.4	1.8
5	2.4	1.8
6	2.4	1.8

1.4.2.3 LOAD LOOP:

The load loop activates the Megawatt compensation loop. It controls to a fixed Megawatt load and changing power demand to compensate for grid variations and main steam pressure or vacuum conditions. It is represented by a digital signal (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998).

1.4.2.4 GOVERNOR VALVES AND ACTUATOR POSITION:

The actuator position indicates how far open the actuators have opened to control the governor valves. At startup, the governor valves are only about 2% open to allow steam required to bring the turbine to synchronisation speed (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998).

1.4.2.5 VALVE POSITION FOR MAIN TURBINE ESVS:

The ESVs are either fully open to admit steam or fully closed in the event of a trip, to prevent the admission of steam to the turbines. The ESVs positions are digital signals indicating open or close. (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual)

1.4.2.6 VALVE POSITION FOR MAIN TURBINE RESVS:

The RESVs, just like the ESVs are either fully closed or fully open. The RESVs position signals are digital, indicating open or close states. (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual)

1.4.2.7 MAIN TURBINE TRIP:

The main turbine trip button causes an immediate closure of all the ESVs and RESVs. The main turbine governor valves and intercept valves also close as a result of the trip. It desynchronises the generator and as a result of closure of all the steam valves, the turbines windmill down to barring speed. A trip of the main turbine will also eventually trip the main boiler feedpump turbine. Turbine trip is represented by a digital signal (Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

1.4.2.8 SIMULATION ENGAGE:

This signal input informs the EHG that the simulator unit is connected. Its major function is to change parameters to factory defaults. It is represented by a switch indicating whether the simulator is connected or not (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

1.4.3 DESCRIPTION AND CHARACTERISATION OF EHG PARAMETERS FROM THE MBFPT:

1.4.3.1 SPEED AND SPEED SETPOINT:

When the turbine is running in speed mode, the main boiler feedpump turbine controls to a speed setpoint specified. The rated speed of the main boiler feedpump turbine is 4380 rpm and the barring speed is 100 rpm. (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998; South of Scotland Electricity Board 2003; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual)

1.4.3.2 VALVE AND VALVE SETPOINT:

When the main boiler feedpump is running in valve mode, the main boiler feedpump turbine controls to a valve setpoint specified (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

1.4.3.3 VALVE POSITION AND ACTUATOR POSITION FOR GOVERNOR VALVES:

The main boiler feedpump governor valves position specify the extent to which the governor valves have opened to admit steam to the main boiler feedpump turbine and the actuator position indicate how open the actuators are to control the governor valves (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

1.4.3.4 VALVE POSITION FOR ESVs:

The ESVs are either fully open to admit steam or fully closed in the event of a trip, to prevent the admission of steam to the turbines (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998; Hunterston 'B' Training Manual).

1.4.3.5 MODE:

There are three control modes for the boiler feedpump turbine:

(i) SPEED MODE:

This mode is primarily used during warming/startup. Under this mode, the main boiler feedpump turbine controls to a speed reference which may be manual (by using the raise/lower buttons to change the speed) or automatic (by using speed reference sent from the unit control computer). It is represented using a digital signal indicating whether or not the feedpump is running in speed mode (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998).

(ii) VALVE MODE:

This is the primary control loop. Here, the main boiler feedpump controls to a valve set point which may be manual (by using the raise/lower buttons to change the speed) or automatic (by using speed reference sent from the unit control computer). It is also represented using a digital signal indicating whether the valve mode is in operation or not (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998).

(iii) BACKUP MODE:

This is a failure mode. If the EHG has failed, the operator can manually open and close the main boiler feedpump steam valves using raise/lower buttons in the Central Control Room (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998).

1.4.3.6 AUTO FEEDWATER MODE:

When this mode is enabled, an analogue input (called feedwater demand) is used as reference. The feedwater demand is sent from the unit control computer and it indicates the speed or valve setpoint. A digital signal is used to indicate whether the feedpump is running in Auto Feedwater mode or not. Alternatively, when the main boiler feedpump is under manual feedwater control, raise/lower buttons are used to change the speed or valve setpoint (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998).

1.4.3.7 MAIN BOILER FEEDPUMP TURBINE TRIP:

A main boiler feedpump turbine trip results in closure of the governor valves and ESVs. A digital signal is used to indicate a turbine trip (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998).

1.4.3.8 SIMULATION ENGAGE:

Just like for the main turbine, the signal input informs the EHG that the simulator unit is connected. Its major function is to change parameters to factory defaults. It is also represented by a switch indicating whether the simulator is connected or not (Rolls Royce Industrial Control Limited, 1998).

1.5 OBJECTIVES:

The following questions that arose at the plant necessitated carrying out this dissertation:

- i. Is it possible to replace the printer at the EHG room with a rack-mounted computer that would provide a data logging facility as well as providing speed signals for testing the governor when required?
- ii. Is it possible to log additional useful parameters from the main turbine and boiler feed pump turbine at every point in time to enable investigations in the event of a trip?
- iii. Is it possible to design a computer network to make the logged data available on the desktops of authorised engineers?

This dissertation aims to answer the questions above by implementing the following specific objectives:

- i. To design a data logging system that acquires and logs EHG signals from the EHG Control System.
- ii. To incorporate simulation functionality for additional signals from the Main Turbine and Main Boiler Feed Pump Turbine Units based on the electrical characteristics of the signals.
- iii. To develop an efficient data logging system to log the simulated EHG signals in ii above.
- iv. To generate configurable speed signals for testing the EHG when it is offline and the unit is on a maintenance outage.
- v. To design a networking strategy that makes the logged and real-time data remotely available to the applicable engineers.

The data logging system developed would be thoroughly tested and proven to be fully functional before it is installed to the plant. This is because the EHG is a vital system that would trip the main turbine in the event of a failure. This would result in lost generation and resultantly, lost revenue to the company.

1.6 ORGANISATION OF DISSERTATION:

Chapter two provides useful background information on data acquisition and analysis techniques related to the dissertation and a detailed outline of the software and hardware to be used in this dissertation. Network concepts used in this dissertation are also explained in this chapter.

Chapter three presents the software design including the simulation of signals, acquisition of EHG signals, simulation of configurable speed signals for testing the EHG and data logging of simulated and acquired signals

Chapter four presents and analyses the EHG data acquired and discusses the simulation results. This chapter also looks at the system performance and identifies limitations to the study.

Chapter five gives the conclusion for the dissertation and recommendations for future work to be carried out on the logging system, including suggested ways of making the logged data remotely available.

CHAPTER TWO

BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter describes different kinds of signals, their sources and gives an introduction to data acquisition. Networking concepts employed in this dissertation are also explained. This chapter also introduces the software and hardware employed in the data acquisition and data logging exercise and gives an overview of LabVIEW software and reasons for choosing the software. The chapter ends by describing the process of setting up hardware required for the data acquisition from the EHG Control System.

2.1 SOURCES OF SIGNALS:

It is usually required to measure different physical quantities like temperature, pressure, flow rate and many others, and convert them into a voltage or current signal for ease of transmission, recording or analysis. The signals are either from transducers or actuators (Johnson, 1997).

2.1.1 TRANSDUCERS:

A transducer is a device that converts the energy from a physical quantity to energy in another form, usually electrical energy. The resulting electrical signal generated is proportional to the physical quantity being measured. As an example, during temperature measurement in an industrial process with a thermocouple, the device generates a voltage that varies with temperature. When signal conditioning and processing functionalities are added to a transducer, it is better referred to as a sensor. (Johnson, 1997; Wallace, 2008; Pugh et al, 2008).

2.1.2 ACTUATORS:

An actuator performs the opposite function of a transducer, by converting a signal (usually electrical) into a physical quantity. Actuators are mostly used to control quantities like temperature, pressure or position.

The response produced in a physical system by actuators is usually nonlinear. As an example, actuators (variable ratio levers) are employed in the controlled admission of steam to the turbines during electricity generation in a nuclear power station. The flow

of steam varies in a nonlinear manner with respect to the actuator position (Johnson, 1997; Wallace, 2008; Pugh et al, 2008).

2.2 CLASSIFICATION OF SIGNALS:

Signals are broadly grouped into analogue or digital signals as show in *Figure 2.1* below.

Figure 2.1: Classification of Signals

2.2.1 ANALOGUE SIGNALS:

Analogue signals change in value as time changes. Examples of analogue signals are Direct Current (DC) signal and Alternating Current (AC) Signal (Johnson, 1997).

2.2.1.1 ANALOGUE DC SIGNALS:

These signals are either fixed or they change very slowly with time. The useful information communicated by these signals is in the amplitude of the signals at any given time. Pressure, temperature, voltage, rate of flow and level measurements are common examples of analogue DC signals. Measuring instruments utilising Analogue to Digital Converters are used to measure the above mentioned signals to give a definite value that represents the size of the signals at a given instant (Johnson, 1997). *Figure 2.2* shows an analogue DC signal.

Figure 2.2: Analogue DC Signal

2.2.1.2 ANALOGUE AC TIME-DOMAIN SIGNALS:

Analogue AC signals pass on useful information about the magnitude (amplitude) of the signal and also variation of the amplitude with time. *Figure 2.3* shows an analogue AC time domain signal.

Figure 2.3: Analogue AC Time Domain Signal

2.2.1.3 FREQUENCY DOMAIN SIGNALS:

It is usually necessary to convert a signal from time domain to frequency domain for a more detailed analysis of the signal. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is a Digital Signal Processing (DSP) function used to effect the conversion. Other DSP functions can be used to analyse important components of the signal like frequency components and noise distribution (Johnson, 1997).

2.2.1.4 JOINT TIME-FREQUENCY (JTF) DOMAIN:

This is a combination of the AC time-domain and frequency domain and the resulting signal is a frequency spectrum that changes with time. Examples of JTF signals are speech, biomedical signals, radar and vibration signals (Johnson, 1997).

2.2.2 DIGITAL SIGNALS:

Digital signals have two states (on or off). Digital data from the signal is composed of active level (on) or inactive level (off) *bits*. Digital signals are further grouped as either *on-off* signals or *pulse train* signals (Johnson, 1997).

2.2.2.1 ON-OFF SIGNALS:

Information regarding the status (on or off) of these signals is most important. With the necessary signal conditioning, these signals can be acquired by a digital port (Johnson, 1997). *Figure 2.4* shows a digital on-off signal.

Figure 2.4: Digital On-Off Signal

2.2.2.2 PULSE TRAIN SIGNALS:

Pulse train signals need to be applied to digital counters to measure their frequency, period or pulse width (Johnson, 1997). *Figure 2.5* shows a digital pulse train signal.

Figure 2.5: Digital Pulse Train Signal

2.3 DATA ACQUISITION:

Data acquisition (DAQ) involves measuring physical variables like temperature, pressure current, length and storing them in a consistent manner, with the aim of monitoring a process, and for further analysis of the stored information.

Before designing and building a data acquisition system, it is important to determine the reason for carrying out the data acquisition task and also how it is intended to analyse the data acquired. If an application is to be developed for carrying out a computer-based DAQ system, it is important to specify the software and hardware required, as well as the rates of sampling (Johnson, 1997; Wallace, 2008; Pugh et al, 2008).

The acquired signal may require *signal conditioning* and *signal processing* to convert the signals to a suitable form. *Figure 2.6* gives a typical schematic for a DAQ system. *Figure 2.7* shows the NI PXI-1042 from NI, which has functionalities for bench-top or rack-mounted test, measurements and control systems. Its design also makes it suitable for tests and data acquisition systems.

Figure 2.6: Typical DAQ Schematic

Figure 2.7: NI PXI-1042 Hardware

2.3.1 SIGNAL CONDITIONING FOR COMPUTER-BASED DAQ:

2.3.1.1 AMPLIFICATION:

Amplification raises the level of acquired physical signals which are usually small in size. DAQ devices have built-in amplifiers to allow for better analogue-to-digital conversion (Johnson, 1997; Pugh et al, 2008).

2.3.1.2 FILTERING:

Filtering involves removal of unwanted signals from the signal of interest. Noise filters can be used with DC signals, like temperature, to block signals of high frequency that interfere with the measurement and reduce accuracy. Antialiasing filters can be used with AC signals, like vibration, to prevent higher frequency signals from interfering with the signal of interest (Pugh et al, 2008).

2.3.1.3 LINEARISATION:

Some transducers exhibit a nonlinear relationship to the physical variable being measured. Examples of such transducers are thermocouples and strain gauges (Pugh et al, 2008).

2.3.1.4 ISOLATION:

For safety reasons, it is necessary to separate the acquired signals from the computer to protect the computer from any high voltage from the signal source. Isolation of the signal also ensures accurate signal acquisition as the DAQ boards are not affected by *ground* loops (Pugh et al, 2008).

2.3.2 ANALOGUE TO DIGITAL CONVERSION:

This is the process of converting an analogue signal into a digital form recognisable by a digital system, for example, a computer. Measurement of temperature, pressure, flow rate and level measurement signals require this conversion. During analogue to digital conversion, the measuring instrument monitors the signal and computes the number of bits (single digital values) needed to represent the signal.

The *resolution* and frequency of sampling are important factors to be considered before carrying out analogue to digital conversion. The resolution is the number of bits used to represent the analogue signal. A greater number of bits correspond to a finer resolution (Johnson, 1997; Wallace, 2008; Pugh et al, 2008).

2.3.3 SAMPLING:

Measuring a time domain signal involves determining the signal shape and also the frequency makeup of the signal. When measuring the signal using digital DAQ devices, the timing of measurements must be accurate to give a good representation of the signal being measured.

Shannon's Sampling Theorem gives a basic rule for sampling signals and according to the rule; the signal must be sampled at a sampling frequency which is greater than twice the highest frequency component present in the signal. For an even better representation of the signal (*Figure 2.9*), the signal should be sampled at a frequency ten times the maximum frequency component of the signal being measured.

If the DAQ device cannot match the rate of change of the signal, *undersampling* results and the measured signal is distorted. Aliasing is a term used to describe distortion of the signal (*Figure 2.10*).

Figure 2.8: Original Sinusoidal Signal

Figure 2.9: Adequately sampling of the signal

Figure 2.10: Dashed lines showing aliasing as a result of inadequate sampling

2.4 SOFTWARE:

LabVIEW, from National Instruments (NI) was used as the programming software used for this exercise.

2.4.1 OVERVIEW OF LABVIEW

LabVIEW stands for Laboratory Virtual Instrument Engineering Workbench. The programming language was developed by NI (Austin, Texas) in 1986. LabVIEW is an important tool used by engineers and scientists in industries. Researchers working in universities and research laboratories have also found LabVIEW very useful. LabVIEW is used on major operating systems and is very popular because cost of testing and manufacturing is considerably reduced. It is used for various forms of data acquisition and analysis, industrial systems automation and control (Johnson, 1997).

LabVIEW programs are called *virtual instruments* (VIs). Unlike text-based programming languages like C++ and JAVA which adhere to a control flow model of code execution, LabVIEW follows a dataflow model when running VIs. LabVIEW however shares aspects of these text-based programming languages like loops, conditional executions and arithmetic operators. LabVIEW has similarities with hardware definition languages like VHDL (*Very High Speed Integrated Circuits Hardware Description Language*), since it can also perform several tasks at the same time. It is easy to learn and use because there are no difficult syntax to adhere to unlike C++ or JAVA. LabVIEW also has many ready made controls that make software development very fast (Johnson, 1997).

2.4.2 DATAFLOW PROGRAMMING WITH LABVIEW:

LabVIEW is fully a graphical programming language and its source code is made up of controls, indicators, nodes and wires. The controls and indicators represent interactive input and output terminals of the VI. The flow of data along the wires determines the order of execution. Not all wires contain the same kind of data and the data is usually formatted appropriately before it is carried by the correct wire (Johnson, 1997).

2.4.3 IMPORTANT LABVIEW FEATURES USED IN THIS DISSERTATION:

Important features of LabVIEW software that were taken advantage of in this dissertation are:

- Integrated drivers and a comprehensive library of functions for serial and parallel computer port as well as network communication protocols.
- Multithreaded execution system utilising queues to communicate data between parallel loops.
- Data logging using a variety of file formats.
- Front panel objects that allow designing of user friendly graphical user interface.
- Simple, efficient and real-time visual debugging feature.
- Effective documentation tools to create descriptions for VIs and their objects, such as controls and indicators, to describe the purpose of the VIs or objects and to give users instructions for using the VI or object.
- Creation of sub VIs (subroutines or methods in text-based programming languages) that allow large block diagrams to be reduced to smaller and easier-to-understand format.
- Quick and Efficient technical support from National Instruments, the developers of LabVIEW software.

2.4.4 LABVIEW VERSION USED IN THIS DISSERTATION:

The LabVIEW version used for this project was version 8.6. Benefits of using this version of LabVIEW for the dissertation were:

- LabVIEW 8.6 has the block diagram cleanup tool which resizes and realigns the items placed on the block diagram
- The version provides the capability of editing multiple objects simultaneously. (National Instruments, 2008)
- VIs created occupy smaller disk space. (National Instruments, 2008)

- LabVIEW 8.6 also comes with the Quick Drop functionality that enables the user to find and place front panel and block diagram objects using predictive text. (National Instruments, 2008)
- Development of high-performance systems capable of parallel processing and parallel measurements. (National Instruments, 2008)

2.5 HARDWARE:

2.5.1 DB-9 FEMALE SERIAL PORT CONNECTOR:

A DB-9 ‘female’ serial port connector (*Figure 2.11*) is used to establish serial link with the ‘male’ serial port at the back of the laptop which would be used to acquire data from the EHG Control System. The DB-9 serial port connector pin assignments are given in *Appendix B*.

Figure 2.11: DB-9 Female Connector

2.5.2 DB-25 SERIAL PORT CONNECTOR:

A DB-25 ‘male’ connector (*Figure 2.12*) is used to establish serial link with the DB-25 serial terminal from the EHG Control System. The DB-25 serial port connector pin assignments are given in *Appendix B*.

Figure 2.12: DB-25 Male Connector

2.5.3 FILE TRANSFER PROTOCOL (FTP) CABLE:

The FTP cable (*shown in Figure 2.13*) is used to connect the DB-9 connector and the DB-25 connector together to establish a serial link between the laptop and the EHG Control System.

Figure 2.13: FTP Serial Cable with DB-9 and DB-25 connectors attached.

2.5.4 LAPTOP:

A laptop with LabVIEW 8.6 installed (*Figure 2.14*), running on Microsoft Windows XP and having a DB-9 male serial connector was used to establish serial connection with the EHG Control System.

2.6 RS 232 SERIAL INTERFACE STANDARD:

Recommended Standard 232 (RS 232) was set-up to allow communication among computer systems in different locations. The standard was developed by a group including the *Electronic Industries Association* (EIA) and gives specifications for the serial interface between *Data Terminal Equipment* (DTE) and *Data Communications Equipment* (DCE). The standard specifies characteristics of electrical signals (voltage levels), characteristics of mechanical interfaces (connectors) and a description of the functions of each electrical signal.

There are two sizes of RS-232 serial ports, namely D-Type 25-pin connector and D-type 9-pin connector. The computer has male versions of these connectors at its back, thus requiring the female version of the connector (Johnson, 1997; Knight, 2009).

Figure 2.14: Data Acquisition setup showing the EHG serial terminal, LA75 Printer, serial cable and Laptop with LabVIEW 8.6

2.7 COMMUNICATION BETWEEN EHG AND LAPTOP/PRINTER:

The EHG Control System is a DCE device. A computer is an example of a DTE device. The EHG Control System transmits data to the LA75 printer (*Figure 2.14*) normally via serial communication. A laptop is connected to the EHG Control System using a serial connection and the standard of serial port communication in use is the RS-232 standard. An RS-232 DB-25 to DB-9 converter (*Figure 2.15*) was built to establish connection between the EHG Control System and the laptop. It consisted of a DB-9 female connector and a DB-25 male connector linked together with an FTP cable. Serial data transfer between laptop and EHG Control System was achieved using only three lines, i.e. transmit line, receive line and the signal ground as shown in *Table 2.1*. The pin numbers of the connector were replaced according to the diagram and table conversion below (Knight, 2009):

Figure 2.15: RS 232 DB-9 to DB-25 Converter

Table 2.1: DB-9 to DB-25 Conversion

DB-9	DB-25	FUNCTION
2	3	Receive Data
3	2	Transmit Data
5	7	Signal Ground

2.8 REQUIREMENTS FOR DATA TRANSFER:

Before serial communication between the laptop and the EHG Control System was possible, it was necessary to specify certain data transfer parameters in LabVIEW. The following parameters were specified using LabVIEW and values assigned to enable connection between the EHG Control system and the computer, using the table conversion above as a guide:

2.8.1 BAUD RATE:

Baud rate measures the speed at which data moves between instruments communicating via serial connection. The EHG Control System which sends data to the *LA75 Plus Companion* Printer has a baud rate set at 1200 bits per second. That means that the *LA75 Plus's* baud rate has to be changed to 1200 in order to have

accurate communication between the EHG Control System and the printer (Digital, 1991)

To receive data from the EHG Control System using LabVIEW software, baud rate was changed to 1200 bits per second as well to enable accurate communication between the EHG and the laptop (Digital, 1991).

2.8.2 DATA BITS:

This is the number of bits used to encode a character (Knight, 2009). It specifies the number of bits in the incoming data. Data bits specified was 8 bits.

2.8.3 PARITY:

This is an optional bit included to provide error handling. It ensures that information has been received correctly. No parity was selected in the data acquisition from the EHG Control System (Knight, 2009).

2.8.4 STOP BITS:

Stop bits provide information to the receiver regarding when each byte of data ends. Stop bits specified was 1 bit. (Knight, 2009)

2.8.5 FLOW CONTROL:

This sets the type of control used by the transfer mechanism. Flow control was not used in data acquisition from the EHG Control System for simplicity.

2.9 NETWORK COMMUNICATION:

In order to establish communication among different computers in a network, the computers need to be connected to different network devices that perform different tasks on the computer network. There may also be a need to control the flow of information across networks.

2.9.1 HUBS/REPEATERS:

Different network cables have specified maximum distance over which they can transfer signals without any distortion in the information contained in the signal. The signal strength diminishes after the signal travels that maximum distance. Repeaters are therefore used in networks to increase the physical length of the network, by

recreating and passing on the information they receive without altering the network's functionality. Repeaters do not have the ability to direct the network traffic in any way.

A hub is a repeater that has several ports and it passes on the signal it receives to all computers that are connected to its ports. Hubs are used in relatively small networks that do not experience heavy network traffics. *Figure 2.16* shows five computers connected to a hub.

Figure 2.16: *Computers connected to a hub using straight-through cables*

When a computer on the network sends data to one of the ports on the hub, that data is sent to all the other ports and all the other computers receive that data. A collision occurs when more than one computer on the network tries to send data at the same time.

2.9.2 SWITCHES:

Switches improve network performance of busy networks by dividing the networks into smaller ones. Unlike hubs, switches know the address of devices connected to it and so can recognise individual computers connected to each of its port.

2.9.3 ROUTERS:

Routers take the functionalities of switches a step further by connecting different networks together to enable communication among computers in the different networks. If it is required to send network data between only two of many computers present in different networks, routers can determine the best method of passing

network data between the two computers. *Figure 2.17* shows connection of switches and a router in a network.

Figure 2.17: Computer Networks with 2 switches and a router

2.9.4 NETWORK CABLES:

Network cables provide connection between computers and network devices. Twisted pair 10 Mega bits (10BASE-T Ethernet) and 100 Mega bits (100BASE-TX Fast Ethernet) cables terminated with Registered Jack 45 (RJ-45), shown in *Figure 2.18*, are most common (Knight, 2009). Data through Ethernet cables is transferred by Carrier Sense Multiple Access/Collision Detection (CSMA/CD). An Ethernet cable connected to a computer has its own transmitter and receiver. A computer is either sending information or receiving information at any point in time. With CSMA/CD, a device wanting to send data listens for data movement on the bus, and sends data when there is no data movement.

Figure 2.18: Twisted pair Ethernet cable with RJ-45 jack

Table 2.2: Ethernet cable pin configuration

Pin No.	Function	Wire Colour
1	Transmit (+)	White-Orange
2	Transmit (-)	Orange
3	Receive (+)	White-Green
4	-	Blue
5	-	White-blue
6	Receive (-)	Green
7	-	White-Brown
8	-	Brown

2.9.4.1 STRAIGHT-THROUGH CABLE:

Straight-through cables can be used to connect computers to a hub or a switch. Hubs operate at *half-duplex* mode, ensuring that data flows in one direction at any given instant. If one of the computers connected to a port on the hub sends data, the hub transmits that same data to all its other ports. A collision occurs when more than one computer attempts to send data at the same time. A straight-through cable shown in *Figure 2.19* below cable is created based on the Ethernet cable pin configuration shown in *Table 2.2* above.

Figure 2.19: Straight-through cable connection

2.9.4.2 CROSSOVER CABLE:

Crossover cables (*Figure 2.20*) are used to connect two computers (or other network devices) together. Crossover cables eliminate collision issues because the Ethernet cable transmitter from one computer (or network device) is directly connected to the receiver of the other Ethernet cable on the other computer (or network device). With this connection, data transfer from either computer to the other takes place in *full-duplex* mode and without any delays arising from collisions.

Figure 2.20: Crossover cable connection

2.9.5 ACCESS LISTS:

Access Lists provide security and controlled access for networks by filtering traffic on the network. Access Lists are specified on routers to determine whether data is routed to certain network destinations or blocked from those destinations.

Extended Access Lists functionalities make it possible to deny or permit network traffic from a specific network address (belonging to a network or a network device) to a specific network address and port, ensuring that only authorised users can access specific data over the network.

Access Lists can also be used to encrypt network traffic between routers for added network security.

For the two networks shown in *Figure 2.21* below, access lists have been placed on the router to deny ‘user 2’ access to ‘network 2’. ‘User 1’ however is allowed access to ‘network 2’.

Figure 2.21: Use of Access List on a router to filter traffic between 2 networks

CHAPTER THREE

SOFTWARE

This chapter looks at the steps used to build the LabVIEW application, and the mechanisms that have been put in place to enable authorised users of the software with LabVIEW experience to modify or update the software in future.

3.1 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT ANALYSIS:

An analysis of the requirements of the proposed software, in line with the project aims and objectives was carried out. It was ensured the following tasks stated below were achievable using LabVIEW 8.6:

- (i) Simulation of start-up, loading, steady state and shut down of the main turbine to provide different EHG parameters for logging.
- (ii) Incorporation of a data logging mechanism in the software that logs EHG signals and maintains a separate log record in the event of a turbine trip.
- (iii) Generation of Configurable Speed Signals that can be used to test the EHG when there is a maintenance outage at the station and the EHG is offline.
- (iv) Acquisition and Logging of real-time Data from the EHG using a serial link.

3.2 SYSTEM ANALYSIS:

An analysis was carried out on the suitability of using Windows XP Professional Operating System (OS) for the data acquisition and logging exercise. Windows XP was found to be suitable. LabVIEW 8.6 software was installed on Window XP OS.

3.3 SOFTWARE DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION:

The development of the software was divided into four stages:

- (i) Simulation of EHG parameters
- (ii) Data logging of simulated Signals
- (iii) Generation of Configurable Speed Signals
- (iv) Acquisition and Logging of EHG Data

A user-friendly and highly interactive graphical user interface was designed with consistent use of indicators and controls that were easy to understand. A tabbed pane was used for the front panel and all tabs designed with similar layouts. *Figure 3.1* shows the data flow through the data logging system. The data acquired from the EHG Control system, using LabVIEW, and the LabVIEW simulated EHG parameters are stored on the storage disk of the rack-mounted computer.

Figure 3.1 Data Flow through the Data Logging System

3.3.1 SIMULATION OF EHG PARAMETERS:

Simulation of the EHG parameters was carried out to generate different values of the parameters for different stages of turbine operation. The ‘EHG Parameters’ tab of the EHG_Simulator VI provides the user with controls and indicators to simulate a run-up, de-load and trip of the main turbine. The ‘EHG Parameters’ tab of the software, showing different controls and indicators used for the simulation, is shown in *Figure 3.2*.

Figure 3.2: Front Panel of the software showing the EHG Parameters tab.

3.3.1.1 RUN-UP:

Before run-up of the turbine, the file paths for the log files should be specified under the ‘Data Logging’ tab (*Figure 3.8*). The speed and load setpoints are also the specified (*Figure 3.2*). A rate of increase of the speed is then specified using ‘the raise/lower’ button (*Figure 3.2*). The same ‘raise/lower’ button specifies the rate of increase of load after synchronisation of the turbine. ‘Low Load’ or ‘High Load’ is selected to represent loading either a cold turbine or hot turbine respectively. Speed

setpoints and speed rate are then specified for the main boiler feedpump turbine. Parameters like the load loop, simulation (for main turbine and main boiler feedpump turbine) and Auto Feedwater are also specified (*Figure 3.2*). Finally, a check is made to ensure that all ESVs and RESVs are fully open before run-up.

The run button is pressed and the main turbine speed increases, based on the speed rate specified, until synchronisation speed of 3000 rpm is reached. The operator is then prompted to synchronise the turbine and the 'Synchronised' indicator comes on afterwards. The turbine is block loaded with a load of 20 MW. The intercept valves are fully open at this point and the governor valves open to control subsequent loading of the machine. The electrically powered start and standby boiler feedpumps (SSBFPs) comes into action and the turbine loading increases until the load is about 300 MW at which point the operator is prompted to startup the main boiler feedpump to take over from the SSBFPs. The turbine loading is complete when the load gets to the specified load setpoint. Hunterston 'B' station is currently running at about 70% load capacity and the Load Setpoint is set at 70% by default. *Figure 3.3* and *Figure 3.4* is a flowchart showing an algorithm for simulation of the EHG parameters.

3.3.1.2 DE-LOADING:

If it is required to reduce the generated load, the 'De-Load Target' control is used to specify a value of load to *de-load* to (see *Figure 3.2*). The 'Turbine De-load' button is used to effect the de-loading. The turbine is de-synchronised if it de-loads to the initial block load of 20 MW. The turbine can then be tripped afterwards.

3.3.1.3 TRIP:

The user can simulate a trip of either the main turbine or the main boiler feedpump turbine by pressing either the 'MT Trip' or 'MBFP Trip' button respectively (*Figure 3.2*). Pressing the 'MBFP Trip' button immediately closes all main boiler feedpump vales and brings the main boiler feedpump turbine to its barring speed of 100 rpm. By pressing the 'MT Trip' button, both the main turbine and main boiler feedpump turbine are tripped, resulting in the closure of all main turbine and main boiler feedpump turbine valves, bringing the speeds of both turbines to their respective barring speeds of 30 rpm and 100 rpm.

Figure 3.3: Flowchart representing algorithm for simulation of EHG Parameters (stage I).

Figure 3.4: Flowchart representing algorithm for simulation of EHG Parameters (Stage II).

3.3.2 DATA LOGGING OF SIMULATED SIGNALS:

As the VI runs, simulated EHG parameters are continuously logged to a file (*Cyclic Log File*) and in the event of a turbine trip; a second file (*Trip Log File*) is created (or updated if it already exists), containing information about the state of parameters prior to the trip and moments after the trip. The operator must specify file paths for both files in the 'Data Logging' tab of the software (*Figure 3.2*) before running the VI.

3.3.2.1 CYCLIC LOG FILE:

The *cyclic* log file stores the simulated main turbine and main boiler feedpump turbine parameters as the EHG_Simulator VI runs. It is the source of data for the *trip* log file when a trip situation is simulated.

3.3.2.2 'TRIP' LOG FILE:

This file would help during investigations on causes of the trip. In the simulation software, a 'log' button on the 'Log Simulated EHG Data' section of the 'Data Logging' tab triggers the creation of the separate log file. The operator should press the 'MT Trip' button on the 'EHG Parameters' before initiating a trip logging by pressing the 'Log' button on the 'Data Logging' tab. *Figure 3.5* is a flowchart representing data logging in the event of a trip.

Figure 3.5: Flow Chart representing data logging to Trip Log File

3.3.3 CONFIGURABLE SPEED SIGNALS FOR TESTING EHG:

The frequency of electricity in the UK is 50 Hertz, corresponding to 50 cycles per second (Hunterston ‘B’ Training Manual). The rated speed of the Main Turbine is therefore 3000 rpm.

i.e. 50 revolutions per second x 60 = 3000 revolutions per minute

Acceleration detection level for the EHG is 9% of this rated speed per second. A turbine trip as a result of overspeed occurs when the rate acceleration exceeding 9% per second persists (Rolls Royce Operating and Maintenance Manual, 1998, Hunterston ‘B’ Training Manual).

The ‘Over-Acceleration’ indicator comes on in the ‘Configuration Speed Signals’ tab of the EHG_Simulator VI (shown in *Figure 3.6*) when the sweep rate selected is greater than 9% per second (Rolls Royce Operating and Maintenance Manual, 1998).

Figure 3.7 is a flowchart describing an algorithm for testing a turbine overspeed.

Figure 3.6: Configurable Speed Signals for Testing the EHG

Figure 3.7: Flowchart representing Configurable Speed Signal for testing EHG

3.3.4 ACQUISITION AND DATA LOGGING OF PARAMETERS FROM THE EHG CONTROL SYSTEM:

'THE ACQUIRE AND LOG DATA FROM EHG CONTROL SYSTEM' section of the 'Data Logging' tab is responsible for acquisition and logging of parameters from the EHG Control System. The default settings for the 'EHG SERIAL COMMUNICATION SETUP' shown in *Figure 3.8* should be used because they have been set up in line with the *LA75 Plus Companion* Printer currently being used at the station. The operator must specify a log file destination and name before pressing the 'Log data from EHG' switch. The VI must already be running before the switch is pressed. A Printout of the EHG log file is shown in *Appendix C. Figure 3.9* is a flowchart showing the data acquisition and data logging of EHG parameters from the EHG Control System.

Figure 3.8: Acquisition and Data Logging of EHG Data

Figure 3.9: Flowchart representing data acquisition and logging from EHG Control System

3.3.5 SUB VIs USED IN THE LABVIEW PROGRAM:

All subVIs used in the program are displayed in the figure below. LabVIEW's VI Hierarchy window (shown in *Figure 3.10 below*) displays the calling hierarchy for the VI and subVIs in the program. Block diagrams for all VIs used can be found in *Appendix D*.

Figure 3.10: VI Hierarchy of Software

3.4 SOFTWARE TESTING:

As part of the software design process, there was functionality testing of smaller units of the software and a testing of the assembled unit. The simulation, Data Logging, EHG data acquisition components of the VI were tested as a unit.

The main VI block diagram was only assembled after all the subVIs were tested and found to be fully functional.

The VI incorporates exception handling mechanisms to handle error situations that arise, for example a wrong log file name or file path. The error handling mechanism gives information regarding the source of the error, the likely cause, steps to be taken to correct the error and an action to take to break out from that error situation (Johnson, 1997).

3.5 SOFTWARE DOCUMENTATION:

Detailed software documentation was provided by creating descriptions for the VIs and their objects, such as controls and indicators, to describe the purpose of the VI or object and to give users instructions for using the VI or object. This was to make the software as interactive as possible because a software documentation of the LabVIEW applications is just as important as having a well-structured and designed application (Johnson, 1997). A breakdown of the documentation is as follows:

3.5.1 DESCRIPTIONS FOR VIs:

Descriptions for all VIs have also been provided to give the user information about VIs and their functions. The VI description appears in the ‘Context Help’ window when the user moves the cursor over the VI on the EHG_Simulator Block Diagram.

Figure 3.11: Description of the visa sub VI in the ‘Context Help’ window of the EHG_Simulator Block Diagram

3.5.2 DESCRIPTION FOR VI OBJECTS:

Description for all the objects was provided to give the user information about the front panel controls and indicators. The object description appears in the ‘Context Help’ window of the block diagram when the user moves the cursor over the object as shown in *Figure 3.12* below.

Figure 3.12 Description of the Turbine Speed Gauge in the ‘Context Help’ window of the EHG_Simulator Block Diagram

3.5.3 TIP STRIP:

When the software user moves the cursor over a front panel object while the VI is running, brief descriptions of the object appear as a tip strip to give the user more information about the object as shown in *Figure 3.13* below.

Figure 3.13: Tip Strip for the ‘Setpoint Raise/Lower’ button while VI is running

3.5.4 DESCRIPTION FOR BLOCK DIAGRAMS:

In addition to descriptions of the objects in the 'Context Help' window, descriptions are provided in different sections of block diagram of the VIs and sub VIs to provide a better understanding of the block diagram design. This makes it easier for enhancements to be carried out the software by authorised persons. *Appendix D* shows the block diagrams of the VIs and their descriptions.

3.6 SOFTWARE DEPLOYMENT:

The software was tested and found to be fully functional. However, modifications to the software have to be made to allow real-time acquisition of EHG signals from a rack-mounted computer connected to the EHG Control Unit. The software would only be deployed after all necessary considerations regarding the implications of deploying the system have been made and approval from the relevant authorities at the station has been obtained.

3.7 SOFTWARE MAINTENANCE/ENHANCEMENT:

It is important to carry out periodic monitoring and maintenance of the data logging software after deployment, to achieved continued optimum performance of the software. It may also be necessary to carry out updates to the software, to benefit from improved functionalities from the updates. There are experienced LabVIEW users at the station that can perform updates to the LabVIEW software and carry out necessary enhancement to software design.

CHAPTER FOUR

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

4.1 CONFIGURABLE SPEED SIGNALS:

4.1.1 INDEPENDENT SPEED SIGNAL:

A sampling rate of 8000 Hz was chosen, in line with Shannon Sampling Theorem, to give a good representation of the *switchable* independent speed signal. The signal has two component frequencies, 8 Hz and 800 Hz representing turbine barring speed (30 rpm) and speed of the turbine at synchronisation (3000 rpm). *Table 4.1* shows the configuration for the independent speed signal.

Table 4.1: Independent Speed Signal Configuration

Electrical Characteristics	Value
Minimum amplitude	5 Volts
Maximum amplitude	12 Volts
Form	Sinusoidal
Output Impedance	approximately 100 Ohms
Switchable	8 Hz or 800 Hz

The switchable frequency values of 8 Hz and 800 Hz correspond to turbine frequencies at barring speed and at synchronising speed respectively.

Barring Speed:

At barring speed, the turbine shaft at a rate of 30 rpm

30 revolutions per minute corresponds to $30 \div 60$ revolutions per second

For 16 toothed turbine wheel, frequency = $(30 \div 60) \times 16$ per second = 8 Hz.

Synchronising Speed:

At synchronising speed, the turbine runs at a speed of 3000 rpm

3000 revolutions per minute corresponds to $3000 \div 60$ revs per second

For 16 toothed turbine wheel, frequency = $(3000 \div 60) \times 16$ per second = 800 Hz.

Simulation of this signal was carried out in LabVIEW. The sinusoidal signal was generated using the Sine Waveform VI shown in *Appendix F*. *Figure 4.1* and *Figure 4.2* show the independent speed signal at frequencies of 8 Hz and 800 Hz respectively.

Figure 4.1: Independent Speed Signal at 8 Hz

Figure 4.2: Independent Speed Signal at 800 Hz

4.1.2 SWEEP SIGNAL:

A sweep signal (chirp signal) is a sinusoidal signal whose frequency varies from an *initial frequency* to a *target frequency* during the period of simulation. Its current value is dependent on the current simulation time. *Table 4.2* shows the configuration of the sweep signal.

Table 4.2: Switchable Sweep Signal Configuration

Electrical Characteristics	Value
Minimum amplitude	5 Volts
Maximum amplitude	12 Volts
Form	Sinusoidal
Output Impedance	approximately 100 Ohms
Adjustable range	8 Hz to 1000 Hz
Soft Switchable sweep	800 Hz rising at 7% per second
	800 Hz rising at 9% per second
	800 Hz rising at 11% per second

General form of a sinusoidal signal is given by:

$$y_1 = A \sin(2\pi ft) \quad (1)$$

where:

$$y_1 = \text{output}$$

$$A = \text{amplitude of the signal}$$

$$f = \text{frequency}$$

$$t = \text{time elapsed}$$

The equation of a chirp signal is given as:

$$y_2 = A \sin(2\pi f(t)t) \quad (2)$$

where:

y_2 = output

A = amplitude of the signal

t = time elapsed

α = rate of rise of frequency (sweep rate)

$f(t)$ is the chirp frequency, given by:

$$f(t) = f_0(1+\alpha t)$$

substituting for $f(t)$ in equation (2) above,

$$y_2 = A \sin(2\pi f_0(1+\alpha t)t) \quad (3)$$

The sweep signal was generated using the Formula Waveform VI in *Appendix D*. A string corresponding to the sweep formula was created and fed as input to the Formula Waveform VI. *Figure 4.3* below shows a snapshot of the sweep speed signal.

Figure 4.3: Sweep Speed Signal

4.2 EHG LOG FILE:

The data acquired from the EHG is sent to the log file in the same format displayed on the EHG monitor. The data format has been pre-programmed by the manufacturers of the EHG Control System. The log file acquired using LabVIEW can however be formatted by the user before being printed out. *Figure 4.4* below shows a screenshot of the EHG Log file and *Appendix C* shows a printout of a page from EHG Log file.

```

data3 - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help

R-R IC V15 Printer Header 13:53:27 31/07/09

R-R IC EHG MAINTENANCE PAGE 2 [ 2] 31/07/09
SETPOINTS & VARIABLES CHANNEL 1 CHANNEL 2 CHANNEL 3 13:53:27
-----
SETPOINTS
SPEED 3000 3000 3000 rpm
LOAD 626 626 626 MW
DEMAND LIMIT (OFF) 692 692 692 MW
MEGAWATT COMPENSATION 156 156 156 MW
VARIABLES
SPEED 2996 2996 2996 rpm

```

Figure 4.4: Screenshot of the EHG Log file

4.3 ‘CYCLIC’ AND ‘TRIP’ LOG FILES:

The format of the log file determines what applications can access the log file. The log file was saved as a text file (*ASCII* text format) to allow for compatibility with a number of text-based or spreadsheet applications. The logged data, which is converted to strings, is structured in a *tab-delimited* format where each value is separated by a tab character and every line ends with a *carriage return*. The first line of the log file contains *tab-delimited* column names corresponding to the names of each parameter. The log files are in a format ready for analysis using spreadsheet applications.

In developing an effective system for data logging of the simulated EHG signals, a number of factors concerning both log files were considered.

4.3.1 CYCLIC LOG FILE:

Each sample containing a complete set of simulated EHG parameters from the main turbine and main boiler feedpump turbine is stored in a single row, with each parameter in its individual cell as seen in the figure below. The parameter values are *tab-delimited* as shown in *Figure 4.5* below.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Date	Time	Speed(rpm)	Speed Setpoint(rpm)	Load(MW)	Load Setpoint(%)	Load Loop(Y/N)	Gov. valve 1(%)	Gov. valve 2 (%)
2	24/08/2009	09:23:02	43	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2
3	24/08/2009	09:23:03	86	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2
4	24/08/2009	09:23:04	129	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2
5	24/08/2009	09:23:05	172	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2
6	24/08/2009	09:23:06	215	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2
7	24/08/2009	09:23:07	258	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2
8	24/08/2009	09:23:08	301	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2
9	24/08/2009	09:23:09	344	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2
10	24/08/2009	09:23:10	387	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2
11	24/08/2009	09:23:11	430	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2
12	24/08/2009	09:23:12	473	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2
13	24/08/2009	09:23:13	516	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2
14	24/08/2009	09:23:14	559	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2
15	24/08/2009	09:23:15	602	3000	0	100	Yes	2	2

Figure 4.5: Snapshot of the cyclic log file showing run up of the turbine at the rate of 43 rpm per minute

4.3.2 TRIP LOG FILE:

This file is created when a trip condition is simulated. The trip file is populated with data from the cyclic log file up to 10 seconds before the trip occurring and another 10 seconds after the trip (*Figure 4.6*). This is to give information on the state of different parameters shortly before and after a trip.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Date	Time	Speed(rpm)	Speed Setpoint(rpm)	Load(MW)	Load Setpoint(%)	Load Loop(Y/N)	Gov. valve 1(%)	Gov. valve 2 (%)
2	24/08/2009	09:36:00	3000	3000	660	100	Yes	100	100
3	24/08/2009	09:36:01	3000	3000	660	100	Yes	100	100
4	24/08/2009	09:36:02	3000	3000	660	100	Yes	100	100
5	24/08/2009	09:36:03	3000	3000	660	100	Yes	100	100
6	24/08/2009	09:36:04	3000	3000	660	100	Yes	100	100
7	24/08/2009	09:36:05	3000	3000	660	100	Yes	100	100
8	24/08/2009	09:36:06	3000	3000	660	100	Yes	100	100
9	24/08/2009	09:36:07	30	3000	0	100	Yes	0	0
10	24/08/2009	09:36:08	30	3000	0	100	Yes	0	0
11	24/08/2009	09:36:09	30	3000	0	100	Yes	0	0
12	24/08/2009	09:36:10	30	3000	0	100	Yes	0	0
13	24/08/2009	09:36:11	30	3000	0	100	Yes	0	0
14	24/08/2009	09:36:12	30	3000	0	100	Yes	0	0
15	24/08/2009	09:36:13	30	3000	0	100	Yes	0	0
16	24/08/2009	09:36:14	30	3000	0	100	Yes	0	0
17	24/08/2009	09:36:15	30	3000	0	100	Yes	0	0
18	24/08/2009	09:36:16	30	3000	0	100	Yes	0	0
19	24/08/2009	09:36:17	30	3000	0	100	Yes	0	0
20	24/08/2009	09:36:18	30	3000	0	100	Yes	0	0
21	24/08/2009	09:36:19	30	3000	0	100	Yes	0	0
22									

Figure 4.6: Snapshot of the Trip Log File

4.3.3 NUMBER OF SAMPLES LOGGED TO THE FILE PER SECOND:

This determines the rate of increase of the log file and ultimately, the log file size at any point in time. A sampling rate of one sample per second was chosen for the simulated parameters.

4.3.4 THE ALLOCATED FILE SIZE OF LOG FILES:

Using a sampling rate of one complete set of samples per second, 10 megabytes of hard disk can be reserved for saving the log files. The figure is arrived at using the calculation below:

Cyclic Log File size:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Size of file with headers alone} &= 610 \text{ bytes} \\
 \text{Size of 1 second worth of data} &= 173 \text{ bytes} \\
 \text{Size of 12 hours worth of data} &= ((12 \times 60 \times 60 \times 173) + 610) \text{ bytes} \\
 &= 7,474,210 \text{ bytes (7.474 megabytes)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Trip Log File size:

Size of file with headers alone	=	610 bytes
Size of 1 second worth of data	=	173 bytes
Size of 20 seconds worth of data	=	((20 x 173) + 610) bytes
	=	4070 bytes (4.070 kilobytes)
Total file size	=	7,478,280 bytes (7.478 mega bytes)

4.3.5 LIFETIME OF THE LOGGED DATA:

The cyclic log file updates itself after every 12 hours. This means that after logging 12 hours worth of data, the cyclic log file is cleared and logging commences all over gain. Each time a trip condition is simulated, the trip log file gets updated with information from the cyclic log file, replacing existing data in the file.

4.4 REMOTE ACCESS TO THE LOGGED DATA:

It is necessary to make the logged and real-time data remotely available to personnel at the nuclear site that require the logged parameters to carry out their day to day job. In view of security policies within a nuclear station, a secure strategy should ensure protection of the logged data from any unauthorised access. Any flaw present in network security hardware, network security implementation or the network design, which has been observed by an intruder, would give the person an opportunity to violate the network policy in place at the station by gaining unauthorised access to the logged files (Bhatnagar, 2007; De Laet and Schuawers, 2005).

It is also important that while trying to implement a strategy to enable remote access of the logged data, no new security loop holes are created. The following methods are considered:

4.4.1 USB DRIVE:

A *USB* (Universal Serial Bus) drive can be used on the rack-mount data logging computer to save the logged data. The saved data can then be transferred to the

computer of authorised persons. Using this method, the risk of data being intercepted by unauthorised persons is negligible.

4.4.2 USE OF ACCESS LISTS:

Figure 4.7: Network connection between rack-mounted computer and an authorised computer

Access lists ensure that there is a secure network communication between the rack-mounted computer and the computer of an authorised user, both highlighted in red. The folder containing the logged files can be shared from the rack-mounted computer and the authorised user can navigate to the folder and access the logged data. If the access list is correctly configured, no other user on the network would be able to access information on either computer as shown in *Figure 4.7* above.

4.4.3 TWO-SYSTEM PEER-TO-PEER NETWORK:

A two-system peer-to-peer network connection can be established between the rack-mount computer and the computer of an authorised user (*Figure 4.8*).

An Ethernet crossover cable can be used to establish direct connection between the rack-mounted computer and the authorised user's computer and since no other computer systems are connected, the data is less likely to be intercepted by an unauthorised user.

Figure 4.8: Peer-to-peer connection between rack-mounted computer and computer of an authorised user

4.5 LIMITATIONS:

The following limitations of this dissertation need to be acknowledged:

- Time constraint prevented a control loop simulation from being carried out. To imitate the system as closely as possible however, the simulation was carried out using values as close as possible to live plant data.
- The format of the acquired and logged data from the EHG Control System, using LabVIEW, was similar to the original format which is normally sent to the printer because the format has been pre-programmed by the manufacturers of the EHG Control System.
- There was no way to test the EHG Control System for overspeed using the configurable speed signal simulated. This was because the plant was fully in operation throughout the time this dissertation was carried out. Such a test would only be possible if the plant is shut down during an outage exercise to carry out inspection and maintenance work on the plant.
- The simulation time taken for turbine run-up, synchronisation, steady-state and de-loading is not the same as the time taken for an actual turbine run-up, synchronisation, steady-state and de-loading. This is because it can take hours to bring the turbine up normally from shut-down in real life.
- The Network strategies suggested were not tested or implemented due to security implications of carrying out such tests at the nuclear station.

CHAPTER FIVE:

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE WORK

5.1 CONCLUSION:

A data logging system was developed that acquires parameters from the EHG Control System. Data logging of simulated main turbine and main boiler feedpump parameters was also carried out.

The data logging system, developed incorporates a mechanism to testing the EHG Control System for overspeed and so eliminates the need for a *function generator* for that purpose.

The data logging system, when implemented, would be more efficient than the previous data logging system as vital data would be captured for future analysis in the event of a turbine trip resulting in a disruption in power generation.

Recommendations have been made for how the acquired data can be made available to authorised persons in a secure manner, considering the network security implications of a nuclear power station.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS:

Suggestions for future work on the data logging system and a strategy for remote access to the logged data are provided below:

5.2.1 INCORPORATION OF A RACK-MOUNTED COMPUTER FOR ACQUISITION OF EHG SIGNALS:

A National Instruments 19 inches rack-mounted computer for acquisition of the EHG parameters should be incorporated with the EHG Control System. The data logging system should be capable of wide range of measurements. The LabVIEW software should be modified accordingly by configuring Data Acquisition for the EHG parameter.

The proposed rack-mounted computer logging the EHG parameters would reside in the EHG room, situated in the turbine hall. Restriction of physical access to the EHG room is already in place at the station. This ensures that only authorised personnel can gain access to the EHG control room and in future would prevent unauthorised persons gaining access to the rack-mounted computer and harming the system or making away with the acquired data using a portable storage device like a USB drive.

5.2.2 REMOVAL OF THE LA75 PLUS COMPANION PRINTER:

The LA75 *Plus* printer is inefficient as it is slow and susceptible to frequent paper jams. It is therefore recommended that the printer be removed. Removal of the printer would also reduce human traffic (for printer repairs and maintenance) to the EHG control room.

5.2.3 LOGGING OF AUTOMATIC VOLTAGE REGULATOR PARAMETERS:

A rack-mount data logging system should also be developed to allow logging of parameters from the Automatic Voltage Regulator (AVR) similar to the one responsible for logging EHG parameters.

5.2.4 CHOICE OF REMOTE DATA ACCESS:

After considering the different methods of making the logged data securely available to authorised users, it is recommended that a USB drive be used to transfer the logged data to the computer systems of authorised users as this method eliminates the potential of introducing security loopholes into the existing computer network at the station.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: POWER GENERATION PROCESS IN AN ADVANCED GAS-COOLED REACTOR NUCLEAR POWER STATION

APPENDIX B: SERIAL PORT CONNECTORS PIN ASSIGNMENTS

APPENDIX C: ACQUIRED EHG PARAMETERS PRINTOUT

APPENDIX D: LABVIEW VI BLOCK DIAGRAMS

APPENDIX A

***POWER GENERATION PROCESS IN AN ADVANCED
GAS-COOLED REACTOR NUCLEAR POWER STATION***

Figure A1.1: Power Generation Process in an Advanced Gas-Cooled Reactor Nuclear Power Station.

APPENDIX B
SERIAL PORT CONNECTORS PIN ASSIGNMENTS

Table A2.1: DB-9 Serial Port Connector Pin Assignments

PIN NUMBER	NAME	DESCRIPTION
1	DCD	Data Carrier Detect
2	RXD	Receive Data
3	TXD	Transmit Data
4	DTR	Data Terminal Ready
5	GND	Signal Ground
6	DSR	Data Set Ready
7	RTS	Request To Send
8	CTS	Clear To Send
9	RI	Ring Indicator

Table A2.2: DB-25 Serial Port Connector Pin Assignments

PIN NUMBER	NAME	DESCRIPTION
1	GND	Shield Ground
2	TXD	Transmit Data
3	RXD	Receive Data
4	RTS	Request to Send
5	CTS	Clear to Send
6	DSR	Data Set Ready
7	GND	System Ground
8	CD	Carrier Detect
9	-	RESERVED
10	-	RESERVED
11	STF	Select Transmit Channel
12	S.CD	Secondary Carrier Detect
13	S.CTS	Secondary Clear to Send
14	S.TXD	Secondary Transmit Data
15	TCK	Transmission Signal Element Timing
16	S.RXD	Secondary Receive Data
17	RCK	Receiver Signal Element Timing
18	LL	Local Loop Control
19	S.RTS	Secondary Request to Send
20	DTR	Data Terminal Ready
21	RL	Remote Loop Control
22	RI	Ring Indicator
23	DSR	Data Signal Rate Selector
24	XCK	Transmit Signal Element Timing
25	TI	Test Indicator

APPENDIX C
ACQUIRED EHG PARAMETERS PRINTOUT

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R-R IC V15                Printer Header                13:53:27  31/07/09

R-R IC                    EHG MAINTENANCE PAGE 2 [ 2]          31/07/09
SETPOINTS & VARIABLES     CHANNEL 1   CHANNEL 2   CHANNEL 3 13:53:27
-----
SETPOINTS
SPEED                    3000        3000        3000 rpm
LOAD                     626         626         626 MW
DEMAND LIMIT (OFF)      692         692         692 MW
MEGAWATT COMPENSATION   156         156         156 MW
VARIABLES
SPEED                    2996        2996        2996 rpm
VACUUM                   (1)         63          64          65 mBar (Abs)
PRESSURE                 (2)         132         133         133 Bar
DROOP COMPENSATION DEMAND 0            0            0 MW
DROOP COMPENSATION X TERM 0            0            0 MW
COMPENSATED PRESS.      160         160         160 Bar
POWER DEMAND             626         626         626 MW
GOVERNOR DEMAND         626         626         626 MW
INTERCEPT DEMAND      1320        1320        1320 MW
    
```

Figure A3.1: Acquired EHG Parameters printout

APPENDIX D
LABVIEW VI BLOCK DIAGRAMS:

Figure A4.2: Log_Data SubVI

Figure A4.3: Sine_Signal1 SubVI

Figure A4.4: visa SubVI

Figure A4.5: Feedpump_Speed SubVI

Figure A4.6: MTTrip_Deload SubVI

Click on a block diagram object and press 'Ctrl + H' for description.

Figure A4.7: Speed_Calculator SubVI

Figure A4.8: EHG_Simulator VI Block Diagram

Figure A4.9: EHG_Simulator VI Block Diagram (Section 1)

Figure A4.10: EHG_Simulator VI Block Diagram (Section 2)

Figure A4.11: EHG_Simulator VI Block Diagram (Section 3)

Figure A4.12: EHG_Simulator VI Block Diagram (Section 12)